

IMPLEMENTATION OF LEARNING CONTINUITY PLAN (LCP) RELATED VARIABLES AMIDST PANDEMIC AND PERFORMANCE OF THE SECONDARY SCHOOLS, DIVISION OF SAN PABLO CITY: INPUT TO QUALITY ASSURANCE

ERWIN G. ABRIL¹

EDEN C. CALLO, EdD²

erwin.abril@deped.gov.ph¹

eden.callo@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0002-9893-8894¹

0000-0002-9457-9361²

Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School¹
Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City Campus²

ABSTRACT

The Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) has been designed with a legal framework responsive to the COVID-19 pandemic, keeping in mind the constitutional mandate to uphold the right of all citizens to quality education at all times. Thus, this descriptive-correlational research design determined the implementation of the LCP and the performance of the 14 principals and 452 teachers in the Secondary Schools, Division of San Pablo City. The results were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, Pearson-r Correlation, t-test, and multiple linear regression analysis. The study revealed that the principals had implemented the LCP implementation-related variables to a great extent, while teachers implemented it to an extent. Both groups of respondents considered the learning delivery modalities, assessment of learning, and learning resources an integral part of the school's performance. The implementation of LCP related variables has a significant relationship with the performance of the school. There were significant differences in the responses of the two groups of respondents on the perceived implementation of LCP. On the other hand, the implementation of LCP variables singly and in combination influenced the school's performance. This study calls for collaboration between schools and stakeholders in implementing LCP as the primary framework in responding to the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: COVID-19, Learning Continuity Plan (LCP), access, quality, governance, school performance